

New European Bauhaus Call for proposals for Citizen Engagement Activities

Project Acronym: SOCIAL4FOOD

**Project title: SOCIAL farming FOR stimulating transgenerational knowledge
transfer and production of typical local FOOD**

Deliverable 1.3: Final report on activity

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¹ Please fill in the contribution table including all of the mandatory Core EIT KPIs in chapter 5.3

1. Executive summary

The SOCIAL4FOOD project aims at applying the principles of the New European Bauhaus to improve the contact between young generations and green public spaces, guided by the wisdom of the elders. Through a series of social farming activities, the project aims to stimulate the involvement of teenagers from the Town of Arsoli (including also young immigrants) in collaboratively farming and cooking a very ancient and high-quality bean typical of this town, named “fagiolina arsolana”.

The main purpose of this deliverable is to describe the final outputs of the project according to the submitted work plan, as well as the identification of potential risks and mitigation measures. One of the outputs is the definition of the co-creation methodology to be applied during all the events planned by the project. Moreover, further outputs resulted from the activities implemented during participatory events held from July to November 2022 in Arsoli.

2. The overall progress of the activity

2.1. Brief description of the activity, main challenges

In this sub-section, a brief description of the realized activities according to the work plan is described.

Activity A1 – Management: the financial, administrative, and technical activities have been carried out. The data management plan (DMP) (Del.1.1), the intermediate report (Del.1.2), and the final report (Del.1.3) have been provided.

Activity A2 – Target group identification, and need analysis: during the open day event organized on July 29th, 2022, the first step of the co-creation of the social farm for the extraction of needs and ideas has been performed. The expected deliverables (Del.2.1 and 2.2) illustrating the call for participation and summarizing the results of the event have been provided. The call for participation in the open-day event is shown below.

 IRPPS Istituto di Ricerche
sulla Popolazione
e le Politiche Sociali con il patrocinio del
Comune di Arsoli eit Community
New European Bauhaus

**INVITO A PARTECIPARE ALL'EVENTO DI
LANCIO del PROGETTO SOCIAL4FOOD**

**Ti piace stare a contatto con la natura e vuoi contribuire a
tramandare la tradizione della fagiolina arsolana?**

**Unisciti a noi per apprendere le pratiche di coltivazione e di
cucina della fagiolina**

**Partecipa ai nostri laboratori collaborativi e contribuisci
anche tu alla realizzazione di un orto sociale**

**TI ASPETTIAMO IL
29 LUGLIO 2022
presso il TEATRO COMUNALE**

**dalle ore 11 alle ore 13: ATTIVITA' per gli
ADOLESCENTI (13-18 anni) e ADULTI
dalle ore 16.30 alle ore 17.30: ATTIVITA' per
BAMBINI 8-12 anni**

SOCIAL4FOOD è un progetto ideato dal CNR-IRPPS e finanziato dalla
Comunità Europea volto a migliorare il contatto tra le giovani generazioni e
gli spazi pubblici verdi, guidati dalla saggezza degli anziani. Attraverso una
serie di attività di agricoltura sociale, il progetto mira a stimolare il
coinvolgimento dei bambini e degli adolescenti arsolani (compresi anche i
giovani immigrati) nella coltivazione e nella cucina collaborativa della
"fagiolina arsolana".

The open-day event represents the first phase of the co-creation methodology based on the design thinking approach. Four different target groups, including local teenagers, local children aged 8-12 years, elders, and local farmers, have been engaged in an attempt to identify experiences and ideas on the growing and cooking of the fagiolina arsolana. Specifically, two different sessions were organized to meet the needs of the different target groups: the former for adults and adolescents and the latter for children. In the first session, dedicated to adults and adolescents, the world café method was applied that consisted of the following activities: collection of experiences, elicitation of ideas, sharing of ideas, and voting of ideas. In the second section, dedicated to children, the storytelling method was applied that consisted of the following activities: storytelling of experiences with emotion definition, collection of tips, and drawings. The results of the discussion allowed us to collect experiences on the growing and cooking of the fagiolina arsolana and needs and ideas for the co-creation of the social farm.

Activity A3 – Co-creation methodology definition: the co-creation methodology has been defined and the expected deliverable (Del.3.1) has been provided. The co-creation methodology is based on the design thinking approach which is a non-linear, iterative process that provides a solution-based approach to solving problems. More details are provided in Section 2.2.

Activity A4 – SOCIAL4FOOD training activities set up, implementation: SOCIAL4FOOD training activities were organized and the expected deliverable (Del.4.1) has been provided. Specifically, the green social laboratories took place on August 18th 2022 and September 24th 2022, the SOCIAL4FOOD competition on September 4th 2022, and the second and third steps of the co-design of the social farm on September 24th 2022 and October 29th 2022. These events constituted the second and third phases of the co-creation methodology based on the design thinking approach. Four different target groups have been involved including local teenagers, local children aged 8-12 years, elders, and local farmers.

GREEN SOCIAL LABORATORIES

Three green social laboratories (i.e., "I learn how to grow the fagiolina", "I learn how to cook the fagiolina", and "I learn how to harvest the fagiolina") were held by local elders and producers to transfer to adolescents, children, and interested citizens their knowledge on:

- the cultivation techniques of the "fagiolina arsolana";
- the cooking of local recipes of the "fagiolina arsolana";
- the harvesting techniques of the "fagiolina arsolana".

In these laboratories, the first, second, and third phases (i.e., concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization) of the learning-by-doing approach were implemented. The laboratories started with the knowledge transfer of cultivation, cooking, and harvesting techniques of the "fagiolina arsolana" from the elderly to participants using storytelling techniques. Participants were actively engaged in the activities, as illustrated in the photos provided in Del. 4.1.

SOCIAL4FOOD COMPETITION

A culinary challenge was held during the "fagiolina festival" involving 5 groups composed of participants in the green social laboratories who tried their hand at cooking typical recipes. In this competition, the last phase (i.e., active experimentation) of the learning-by-doing approach was implemented. Participants were actively engaged in the activities, as illustrated in the photos provided in Del. 4.1.

SECOND STEP OF THE CO-DESIGN OF THE SOCIAL FARM

Starting from the needs and ideas for the co-creation of the social farm gathered during the Open Day event organized on July 29th 2022, each participant was asked to provide some solutions about the organization of the social farm (i.e people to be involved, tasks to perform, etc.). Through a collaborative discussion, a shared solution for the co-design of the

social farm has been provided. Moreover, a group of “Fagiolina Ambassadors” has been appointed to stimulate citizen and stakeholder engagement and participation. For the appointment, representatives for each target group involved in the project (teenagers, children aged 8-12 years, elders, local farmers, and citizens) have been selected according to their commitment to the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities.

THIRD STEP OF THE CO-DESIGN OF THE SOCIAL FARM

During the third co-creation event held on October 29th, 2022, the shared solution about the organization of the social farm emerged during the second co-creation event (specifically people to involve, tasks to perform, etc.) has been illustrated to representatives of the four entities responsible for the management of the social farm in the coming years (the Municipality of Arsoli, Pro Loco of Arsoli, Social elderly center of Arsoli and local farmers of the association “Amici della fagiolina di Arsoli”). A collaboration agreement (provided in Annex A) containing the activities for the management of the social farm, as emerged during the second co-creation event, which each entity is responsible for, has been discussed and signed by representatives of the four involved entities.

Activity A5 – Evaluation, lessons learnt: A survey, consisting of two questionnaires (one for adults and adolescents (see Annex B) and one for children (see Annex C)) and an interview (see Annex D), has been carried out to collect feedback and possible refinements and the expected deliverable (Del.5.1) has been provided. The questionnaires contained a mixture of different items ranging from multiple-choice to Likert-type scales and in some cases provided respondents with the opportunity for free expression. All participants in the SOCIAL4FOOD activities were invited to respond to the questionnaires. Participation in the study was voluntary, and informed consent for participants under 18 years old was obtained by their parents before the questionnaire administration began. To ensure consistency, the questionnaires were designed and printed in the Italian language. The interview was conducted in Italian and administered to the four representatives of the four social entities involved in the project (the Mayor of Arsoli, the President of the social elderly center of Arsoli, the President of Pro Loco of Arsoli, the President of the Association of local producers “Amici della fagiolina di Arsoli”). A video containing an excerpt from the interviews can be visualized at the following Youtube link: <https://youtu.be/og0aVenf4zk>

The answers to the questionnaires and the semi-structured interviews, as well as the discussion, had during the final outreach event with the participants at the round table (four representatives of the social entities involved in the project and two “ambassadors of the Fagiolina Arsolana”) and at the focus group (six local administrators of the neighboring towns), have been analyzed to extract strengths and weaknesses of the project, necessary follow-up activities, and improvements, as described in the following sub-sections. The expected deliverable (Del.5.2) on lessons learnt has been provided. In the following table, the extracted lessons learnt are summarized.

Lesson	Task/Activity/ Output	What worked well and should be	What didn't work and how could it be
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		repeated or scaled up?	improved?
1	Strengthening of the collaboration among the administrative, socio-cultural, and agricultural institutions/associations.	A collaboration agreement has been signed by the abovementioned institutions/associations to manage the maintenance of the social farm and the re-implementation of the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities in the coming years.	Lack of involvement of the school in the collaboration agreement. An awareness-raising strategy should be defined and implemented to stimulate and speed up the bureaucratic process for participating in the re-implementation of SOCIAL4FOOD training activities.
2	Bringing the youth to dialogue with the elders is an effective way of teaching them local cultural traditions.	The project provided a wonderful learning experience for the beneficiaries (mainly children) but also for the teachers (elders and local producers).	Low participation of teenagers in the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities and co-creation events. An effective engagement strategy specifically addressed to adolescents should be developed and implemented by using more digital technologies for attracting their interests.
3	Strengthening community legitimacy in decision-making	The co-creation events helped build understanding and consensus around the social farming design and management.	

Activity A6 – Dissemination and communication: the D&C plan has been defined, the Website of the project has been implemented (<https://cnrirpps.wixsite.com/social4food/en>) and social media are available (<https://www.facebook.com/groups/734039724347222>; <https://twitter.com/Social4foodP>). The final outreach event has been organized in a hybrid way (both online and in presence) on November 26th 2022. Two scientific publications are being drafted and will be submitted to two scientific journals by the end of December 2022.

D&C plan

A document describing the SOCIAL4FOOD dissemination and communication (D&C) strategy and its implementation plan to use for ensuring the high visibility, accessibility, and

promotion of the project and its results has been provided (EO.6.1). Specifically, the objectives of the dissemination and communication activities, target audience, tools and channels, and the expected impacts are illustrated.

Website and social media

The website created and used by the SOCIAL4FOOD project (<https://cnrirpps.wixsite.com/social4food/en>) gives the target audience public access to project resources and activities in addition to providing interested visitors with regular related news. The website will be maintained beyond the end of the SOCIAL4FOOD project to ensure the project's results have sustainable dissemination and impact.

The social media created and used by the SOCIAL4FOOD project are the following:

- 1) a Facebook group (<https://www.facebook.com/groups/734039724347222>) that serves as a platform for discussion, interaction, collection of information, and communication of the project outputs.
- 2) a Twitter account (<https://twitter.com/Social4foodP>) used to inform the broader community about both technical and general information.

Monitoring of the website and social media activities are performed using a set of key performance indicators (KPIs) shown in the following table.

	Expected KPI	Achieved value
Project website	> 40 visitors expected	48 visitors (see Annex E)
Facebook Group	> 60 members joined the group	174 members
Twitter account	> 30 followers of the account	30 followers

Final outreach event

The final outreach event, organized in a hybrid way (both online and in presence) on November 26th 2022, has been attended by 61 people (45 participants online and 16 participants in presence). During the event, the obtained results from the SOCIAL4FOOD project have been shown to participants. A round table with the Mayor of Arsoli and the Mayors of the neighboring towns (Agosta, Anticoli Corrado, Camerata Nuova, Riofreddo, and Rocca Canterano) has been carried out to transfer the co-creation methodology used in the project for stimulating the transfer of transgenerational knowledge and the production of the typical local food of the other territories.

Scientific publications

Two scientific articles showcasing project outputs are in the process of being drafted and will be submitted to two topic-specific open-access journals (Sustainability <https://www.mdpi.com/journal/sustainability> and Societies <https://www.mdpi.com/journal/societies>) by the end of December 2022.

Short promotional video

Three short promotional videos introducing the project, its partnership, and activities have been created and posted on Youtube (<https://www.youtube.com/@social4foodproject>) and the project website for maximum visibility.

Brochures

A brochure (150 copies) containing the activities and results of the project has been created and distributed to the Arsoli community (see Annex F).

Local press

Three online articles have been published in the online press. The links to the articles are provided below:

<https://www.confinelive.it/ad-arsoli-al-via-il-nuovo-progetto-social4food/>

<https://www.confinelive.it/la-cultura-della-fagiolina-arsolana-al-via-i-progetto-social4food/>

<https://www.confinelive.it/ad-arsoli-di-scena-la-fagiolina-con-il-laboratorio-tu-lo-sa-che-so-le-conocchie/>

2.2. Methodology of the engagement with local stakeholders

For the engagement of local stakeholders, a co-creation methodology has been defined for stimulating the transgenerational dialogue and establishing a process of contamination, inspiration, and sharing of ideas.

The co-creation methodology is based on the design thinking approach which is a non-linear, iterative process that provides a solution-based approach to solving problems. The design thinking approach is extremely useful when used to tackle complex problems and it serves to understand the human needs involved, reframe the problem in human-centric ways, create numerous ideas in brainstorming sessions, and adopt a hands-on approach to prototyping and testing. The approach, proposed by the Hasso Plattner Institute of Design at Stanford (2019), is composed of five stages:

- Empathize: research users' needs
- Define: state users' needs and problems
- Ideate: challenge assumptions and create ideas
- Prototype: start to create solutions
- Test: try your solutions out

The five stages of the design thinking approach have been applied during the events planned within the project, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The design thinking approach followed in the SOCIAL4FOOD project

2.2.1. Emphasize and define

The first stage (emphasize and define) is applied during the Open day event, in which local teenagers, children aged 8-12 years, elders, and local farmers are involved in the (i) storytelling of experiences on the growing and cooking of the "fagiolina arsolana" and (ii) elicitation of ideas.

Specifically, two different sessions are organized to meet the needs of the different target groups: the former for adults and adolescents and the latter for children.

2.2.1.1. SESSION for ADULTS and ADOLESCENTS

In the first session, dedicated to adults and adolescents, the world café method is applied consisting of the following activities: collection of experiences, elicitation of ideas, sharing of ideas, and voting of ideas.

Collection of experiences

Participants are asked to answer the following triggering questions, according to their experiences:

- 1) What is your most significant experience in the GROWING of the "fagiolina arsolana" (or in the growing of agricultural products in general)? What difficulties have you encountered? What were the positive aspects?

2) What is your most significant experience in the COOKING of the “fagiolina arsolana” (or of the typical cuisine of Arsoli in general)? What difficulties have you encountered? What were the positive aspects?

Different groups of participants are formed, taking care to include at least one member of each target user for each group: adult, adolescent, man, and woman.

Each person has a maximum of 3 minutes available to tell their experience. After 20 minutes, each participant has 10 minutes to write a brief description of the experience (2-3 sentences), positive aspects, and the encountered difficulties on three post-its. The post-its are attached to a poster for the final discussion.

Elicitation of ideas

Participants are asked to answer the following triggering questions, according to their ideas:

- 1) How to pass on the experience and skills necessary for the traditional growing and cooking of the “fagiolina arsolana” from local elders to adolescents?
- 2) How to stimulate the involvement of local teenagers (including young immigrants) in the collaborative growing and cooking of the “fagiolina arsolana”?
- 3) How would you like to organize the social farm? Who should be involved? How should the tasks be performed?

The different groups of participants appoint a spokesperson who illustrates the emerging ideas and a secretary who reports the ideas, on a sheet.

The group has a maximum of 10 minutes available for discussing and proposing ideas by answering the 3 triggering questions.

Sharing of ideas

The post-it containing the different ideas that emerged from the group’s discussion is put on a poster and the spokesperson of each group explains the ideas that emerged for each question.

Voting of ideas

Each participant is provided with 6 stickers to apply to the 2 ideas that he/she considers most relevant for each question (according to the level of appreciation). At the end of the vote, the most significant ideas are summarized.

2.2.1.2. SESSION for CHILDREN

In the second section, dedicated to children, the storytelling method is applied consisting of the following activities: storytelling of experiences with emotion definition, collection of tips, and drawings.

Storytelling of experiences

Two rounds of storytelling are organized: the former for the experiences in the cultivation of the “fagiolina arsolana” and the latter for its cooking.

In the first round, participants are divided into 3 groups; they are asked to tell their experience with the growing of garden products (in particular the “fagiolina arsolana”) to the other group members. Some possible examples are given (I sowed vegetables with my father/grandfather, I attended the bean harvest event, I sowed seedlings with my teachers, etc.). After the storytelling, participants are asked to write 1-2 sentences to describe their experience. Finally, each participant is provided with 5 stickers representing smiles with emotions (very happy, happy, indifferent, sad, and very sad) and is asked to apply them to the written experience (according to their level of satisfaction).

In the second round, the same process is followed focusing on the experiences in the cooking of the “fagiolina arsolana”.

Collection of tips

Participants are asked to answer the following triggering questions, according to their ideas:

- 1) What would you like to do to learn how to grow the “fagiolina arsolana”?
- 2) What would you like to do to learn how to cook the “fagiolina arsolana”?

Some possible examples are given (e.g., cultivating a vegetable garden with my companions, making a laboratory to learn, listening to the stories experienced by the elderly, etc.).

Drawings

Each participant is asked to realize a drawing for representing his/her experience.

2.2.2. Ideate

The second stage (ideate) is applied during the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities (green social laboratories, SOCIAL4FOOD competition, and the second co-creation event of the social farm), in which local teenagers, children aged 8-12 years, elders, and local farmers are involved in.

During the green social laboratories and SOCIAL4FOOD competition, the “learning-by-doing” is applied, which is an educational approach expounded by Paulo Freire (1982). It is a hands-on learning approach in which participants interact with their environment and actually “do” the activity to adapt and learn. The learning-by-doing approach is composed of the following four phases, as defined by Kolb (1984): (1) having a concrete experience followed by (2) observation of and reflection on that experience which leads to (3) the formation of abstract concepts (analysis) and generalizations (conclusions) which are then (4) used to test a hypothesis in future situations, resulting in new experiences.

The four phases of the learning-by-doing approach applied in the project are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The learning-by-doing approach followed in the SOCIAL4FOOD project

A brief description of each phase is provided below.

Concrete experience

This activity starts with the knowledge transfer of cultivation techniques/cooking recipes of the “fagiolina arsolana” from the elderly to participants using storytelling techniques. Participants learn about the experience told by elderly and local farmers watching them in action. To acquire new knowledge, participants are actively engaged in cultivation/cooking activities.

Reflective observation

This phase in the learning cycle allows participants to discuss the experience with others. Communication at this stage is vital, as it allows participants to identify any discrepancies between their understanding and the experience itself. Participants are divided into groups and are invited to discuss their concrete experiences by highlighting the difficulties and the necessary improvements in the acquired knowledge.

Abstract conceptualization

In this phase, participants move from reflective observation to abstract conceptualization by classifying concepts and forming conclusions on the experience. They are asked to take notes about the concepts and knowledge acquired during the concrete experience (experience notes).

Active Experimentation

This phase in the cycle is the testing stage. Participants have a new cultivation/cooking experience in which they apply the concepts and knowledge acquired during the concrete experience phase (written in their experience notes).

2.2.2.1. GREEN SOCIAL LABORATORIES

Three different green social laboratories (i.e., "I learn how to grow the fagiolina", "I learn how to cook the fagiolina", and "I learn how to harvest the fagiolina") are organized by local elders and producers to transfer to adolescents, children, and interested citizens their knowledge on:

- the cultivation techniques of the "fagiolina arsolana";
- the cooking of local recipes of the "fagiolina arsolana";
- the harvesting techniques of the "fagiolina arsolana".

In these laboratories, the first, second, and third phases (i.e., concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization) of the learning-by-doing approach are implemented.

2.2.2.2. SOCIAL4FOOD COMPETITION

A culinary challenge among different groups composed of participants in the green social laboratories is organized during the "fagiolina festival". Participants try their hand at cooking typical recipes by applying the concepts and knowledge acquired during the culinary laboratory.

In this competition, the last phase (i.e., active experimentation) of the learning-by-doing approach is implemented.

2.2.2.3. CO-CREATION OF THE SOCIAL FARM

Starting from the needs and ideas for the co-creation of the social farm gathered during the Open Day event organized on July 29th 2022, each participant is asked to provide some solutions about the organization of the social farm (e.g. people to involve, tasks to perform, etc.). Through a collaborative discussion, a shared solution for the co-design of the social farm is provided. Moreover, a group of "Fagiolina Ambassadors" is appointed to stimulate citizen and stakeholder engagement and participation. For the appointment, representatives for each target group involved in the project (teenagers, children aged 8-12 years, elders, local farmers, and citizens) are selected according to their commitment to the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities.

2.2.3. Prototype

The third stage (prototype) is applied during the third co-creation event held on October 29th 2022, in which the shared solution about the organization of the social farm emerged during the second co-creation event (specifically people to involve, tasks to perform, etc.) has been

illustrated to representatives of the four entities responsible for the management of the social farm in the coming years (the Municipality of Arsoli, Pro Loco of Arsoli, Social elderly center of Arsoli and local farmers of the association “Amici della fagiolina arsolana”). The collaboration agreement containing the activities for the management of the social farm, as emerged during the second co-creation event, which each entity is responsible for, has been discussed and signed by representatives of the four involved entities.

2.2.4. Testing

During the last stage (testing) of the design thinking approach, a qualitative survey (questionnaires and interviews) for acquiring feedback from participants in the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities is administered.

2.3. Work plan of the activities

The following table summarizes the activities planned in the work plan, and the expected and achieved outputs.

Activity	Description	Duration	Expected outputs/deliverables	Achieved Outputs
A1. Management	Financial, administrative, and technical management; data management plan (DMP)	M1 – M5	EO1.1 Project reports, EO1.2 DMP Del.1.1: DMP (M1) Del.1.2: Intermediate report (M3) Del.1.3: Final report (M5)	- Definition of the DMP (Del.1.1) - Intermediate report (Del.1.2) - Final report (Del.1.3)
A2. Target groups identification, need analysis	2.1 Call for participation: target groups identification 2.2 Open day event: needs analysis and ideas elicitation	M1	EO2.1 List of participants EO2.2 List of needs and ideas Del.2.1: Call for participation (M1) Del.2.2: Results of the Open day event (M1)	- Definition of the call for participation (Del.2.1) - Open day event organized and first step of the co-creation of the social farm for the extraction of needs and ideas performed (Del.2.2)
A3. Co-creation methodology definition	3.1 Definition of the co-creation strategy, planning of activities	M1	EO3.1 Plan of the co-creation activities Del.3.1: Co-creation strategy (M1)	- Definition of the co-creation methodology (Del.3.1)

<p>A4. SOCIAL4FOOD training activities setting up, implementation</p>	<p>4.1 Setting up of the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities 4.2 Green social laboratories 4.3 SOCIAL4FOOD competition 4.4 Co-creation of the social farm</p>	<p>M2-M4</p>	<p>EO4.1 Green social laboratories (M4) EO4.2 SOCIAL4FOOD competition (M4) EO4.3 social farm co-designed (M4) Del.4.1: Results of the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities (M4)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Green social laboratories organized - SOCIAL4FOOD competition organized - Social farm co-designed - Results of the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities (Del.4.1)
<p>A5. Evaluation, lessons learnt</p>	<p>5.1 Results Analysis and evaluation: Qualitative survey for feedback and possible refinements 5.2 Lessons learnt identification</p>	<p>M4-M5</p>	<p>EO5.1 List of feedback and necessary refinements (M5) EO5.2 Set out of Lessons learnt (M5) Del.5.1: Results of Qualitative survey (M5) Del.5.2: Lessons learnt (M5)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Results of Qualitative survey (Del.5.1) - Lessons learnt (Del.5.2)
<p>A6. Dissemination and communication</p>	<p>6.1 Definition of the Dissemination and Communication (D&C) plan 6.2 Final outreach event for the general public; website and social media 6.3 1 Scientific publications</p>	<p>M1-M5</p>	<p>EO6.1 D&C plan (M1) EO6.2 Website and social media (M1) EO6.3 Final outreach event (M5) EO6.4 1 scientific article (M5)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website and social media available (https://cnrirpps.wixsite.com/social4food/en; https://www.facebook.com/groups/734039724347222; https://twitter.com/Social4foodP) - Definition of the D&C plan - Final outreach event organized (both in presence and online) - 2 scientific articles in progress

2.4. Achievement of the objectives

The project defined three specific objectives and related expected outcomes described in the following table. The level of achievement of the specific objectives is provided in the last column of the table.

Specific Objectives (SO)	Expected Outcomes (EO)	Measurements/Target value	Achieved value
<i>SO1: Engagement of citizens and key stakeholders in SOCIAL4FOOD training activities</i>	<i>EO1: Participation of local teenagers, children, and interested citizens in SOCIAL4FOOD training activities taught by local elders and farmers (realised in Activity A2 and A4, del. 2.2 and 4.1)</i>	<i>- Number of local citizens involved in the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities > 70 (10 teenagers, 40 children (9-12 years), 10 elders, and 10 citizens)</i>	<i>The total number of citizens and key stakeholders involved in the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities organized in July, August, September, and October 2022 is 118. Specifically, 3 teenagers, 38 children, 13 elders, 57 citizens, and 7 local farmers.</i>
<i>SO2: Re-purposing of abandoned green spaces</i>	<i>EO2: Realisation of an inclusive and sustainable social farm (realised in Activity A4, del. 4.1)</i>	<i>- 1 vegetable garden for the growth of the "fagiolina" - 1 information stand with brochures illustrating the high quality of the "fagiolina"</i>	<i>- 1 vegetable garden for the growth of the "fagiolina" available - 1 information banner and brochures available</i>
<i>SO3: Experimenting with a citizen engagement strategy to promote the culture and knowledge of typical local foods and traditional agricultural knowledge for replicating it in other similar contexts</i>	<i>EO3: Co-creation methodology to design the social farm, lessons learnt (realised in Activity A3 and A5, del. 3.1 and 5.2)</i>	<i>- Number of participants in the co-design process > 80</i>	<i>The citizen engagement strategy defined in Del.3.1 allowed the achievement of a final number of participants in the co-design process equal to 118.</i>

Therefore, all the specific objectives have been achieved. Indeed, a vegetable garden for the growth of the "fagiolina" has been realized and the number of participants involved in the

SOCIAL4FOOD training activities and the co-design process is greater than the target values (i.e 70 people for SO1 and 80 people for SO3). Although the achieved number of participants is higher than the threshold (118 people involved), it is important to highlight that, the SO1 target values for the specific target groups have been only partially achieved since the number of teenagers and children involved is less than the target value (3 teenagers have been involved instead of 10, and 38 children instead of 40).

3. Outputs and outcomes of the Project

3.1. Identification and prioritization of challenges

The activities implemented within the SOCIAL4FOOD project contributed to the achievement of the expected impacts of the challenge “Re-connecting with nature” in the following ways:

Expected Impact 1: co-design of a social farm for re-purposing an abandoned green space and improving the aesthetics of the territory and the quality of life of the local community.

Expected Impact 2: implementation of the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities to promote the interaction and collaboration between different social groups

In the following table, the KPIs defined for assessing the achievement of these impacts and the achieved value of the KPIs are illustrated.

<i>Expected IMPACTS</i>	<i>KPIs- target value</i>	<i>Achieved value</i>
Expected Impact 1	N° of local citizens and stakeholders involved in the process > 70 Citizen satisfaction degree > 70%, evaluated using a qualitative survey	The local citizens and stakeholders involved in the co-design of the social farm were 118. Citizen satisfaction degree = 81.8%, evaluated according to the percentage of responses given to a question of the qualitative survey performed in November.
Expected Impact 2	N° of social groups involved > 3	The social groups involved in the implementation of the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities were the following five: teenagers, children (9-12 years), elders, citizens, and farmers.

Therefore, EO1 and EO2 have been achieved. Indeed, the achieved values of the KPIs are greater than the target values (i.e 70 people and 70% of citizen satisfaction degree for EO1 and 3 target groups for EO2).

3.2. Ideation process to co-create solutions for the most pressing challenges

To co-create the social farm for re-purposing an abandoned green space and improving the aesthetics of the territory and the quality of life of the local community, an ideation process based on the design thinking approach has been followed. A detailed description of the followed approach is provided in Section 2.2 and Deliverable 3.1.

3.3. Achievement of the outputs, compliance with the Application Form

The project defined several expected outputs for each activity planned in the application form. In the following table, the expected outputs and the achieved outputs are illustrated.

Expected outputs/deliverables	Achieved Outputs
<p>EO1.1 Project reports, EO1.2 DMP Del.1.1: DMP (M1) Del.1.2: Intermediate report (M3) Del.1.3: Final report (M5)</p>	<p>- Definition of the DMP (Del.1.1) - Intermediate report (Del.1.2) -Final report (Del.1.3)</p>
<p>EO2.1 List of participants EO2.2 List of needs and ideas Del.2.1: Call for participation (M1) Del.2.2: Results of the Open day event (M1)</p>	<p>- Definition of the call for participation (Del.2.1) - Open day event organized and first step of the co-creation of the social farm for the extraction of needs and ideas performed (Del.2.2)</p>
<p>EO3.1 Plan of the co-creation activities Del.3.1: Co-creation strategy (M1)</p>	<p>- Definition of the co-creation methodology (Del.3.1)</p>
<p>EO4.1 Green social laboratories (M4) EO4.2 SOCIAL4FOOD competition (M4) EO4.3 Social farm co-designed (M4) Del.4.1: Results of the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities (M4)</p>	<p>- Green social laboratories organized - SOCIAL4FOOD competition organized - Second step of the co-design of the social farm - Third step of the co-design of the social farm - Results of the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities (Del. 4.1)</p>
<p>EO5.1 List of feedback and necessary refinements (M5) EO5.2 Set out of Lessons learnt (M5) Del.5.1: Results of Qualitative survey (M5) Del.5.2: Lessons learnt (M5)</p>	<p>- Results of Qualitative survey (Del.5.1) - Lessons learnt (Del.5.2)</p>

<p>EO6.1 D&C plan (M1) EO6.2 Website and social media (M1) EO6.3 Final outreach event (M5) EO6.4 1 scientific article (M5)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website and social media available (https://cnrirpps.wixsite.com/social4food/en; https://www.facebook.com/groups/734039724347222; https://twitter.com/Social4foodP) - Definition of the D&C plan - Final outreach event organized (both in presence and online) - 2 scientific articles in progress
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3.4. Impact of the activity

The activity carried out in the project had a great social impact. In particular, the engagement of citizens and key stakeholders in both the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities and the co-design of the social farm allowed the Arsoli community to build a transgenerational dialogue and establish a process of productive contamination, inspiration, and shared ideas between older and younger generations.

The SOCIAL4FOOD training activities, and in particular the green social laboratories, also allowed to stimulate the reconnection between people and the natural environment by stimulating physical and psychological well-being. Moreover, they fostered social relationships and the aggregation opportunity, dramatically reduced by the Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic and the widespread use of smartphones and other digital technologies that lead people to detach themselves from nature.

Another great social impact of the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities was the maintenance and recovery of traditional agricultural knowledge and the sustainable practices of the "fagiolina" production through the knowledge transfer of the typical recipes of the "fagiolina" and the experiences and skills needed for its growth.

Finally, the realized vegetable garden provides social inclusion opportunities to people building a sense of community and belonging and improving the well-being and quality of life by offering a calming environment, away from the pressures of everyday life that help to release stress.

4. Conclusion, lessons learnt and recommendations

4.1. Overall management process and risk mitigation

The timing of the activities is in line with the proposed work plan.

All the planned deliverables have been completed and submitted.

All the final outcomes have been achieved. Specifically, the total number of citizens and key stakeholders involved in the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities is more than 70 and the total number of participants in the co-design process is more than 80. More in detail, considering the KPIs defined in the Application form for each target group, all the thresholds have been satisfied, except for the adolescent target group. Specifically, the following target group participated in the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities: 38 children instead of 40, 3 teenagers instead of 10, 57 citizens instead of 10, and 20 elders instead of 10 (of which 7 farmers). The

main reason for the low participation of the adolescent target group, as told by the 3 teenagers involved, is the high school and extracurricular commitments that affect a lot of voluntary and active participation in social and cultural activities, like those organized by the project. Moreover, another reason is the lack of active participation of the school in the project which didn't allow to systematically involve the adolescents. In fact, during the first 3 months of the project, the school was closed for the summer holidays and in the remaining 2 months, the school required an extensive bureaucratic process to have permission to participate in external projects. Specifically, the participation by the school in "additional" projects to the ordinary teaching activities must be included in the educational offer plan drawn up by the teaching staff in October and approved by the school council. The request to participate in the project activities was sent to the school in early October, but the school did not respond by the end of the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities (on October 29, 2022). The school approved the inclusion of the SOCIAL4FOOD project activities in the educational offer plan for the current school year at the end of November 2022. Therefore, the school will contribute to the maintenance of the social farm and the replication of the project activities in the coming year.

4.2. Recommendations for the replication and/or upscaling up of the realized activity

The following recommendations for the replication and/or upscaling up of the realized activity resulted from the project's results:

- Periodical meetings with the local administrators of the neighboring towns to continue the process of scaleup of the project activities in the neighboring territory to stimulate the transgenerational knowledge transfer and production of their typical local food;
- Periodical meetings with representatives of the social entities, who signed the collaboration agreement, the school, and the "ambassadors of the Fagiolina Arsolana" to support them and ensure everyone understood the objectives and commitments to maintain the social farm and replicate the project activities in the coming years.

5. Annexes

5.1. Evidences that describe the achievement of KPIs²:

5.1.1. Summary of good practices and lessons learnt (EITHE 14.1)

One best practice has been defined, which is the co-creation methodology (Activity 3), which was validated by using a qualitative survey.

Three lessons learnt from the implementation and follow-up of the co-creation methodology during the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities are identified and codified according to the

² Please fill in the contribution table including all of the mandatory Core EIT KPIs in chapter 5.3

results of the qualitative survey. In the following table, the extracted lessons learnt are summarized.

Lesson	Task/Activity/Output	What worked well and should be repeated or scaled up?	What didn't work and how could it be improved?
1	Strengthening of the collaboration among the administrative, socio-cultural, and agricultural institutions/associations.	A collaboration agreement has been signed by the abovementioned institutions/associations to manage the maintenance of the social farm and the re-implementation of the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities in the coming years.	Lack of involvement of the school in the collaboration agreement. An awareness-raising strategy should be defined and implemented to stimulate and speed up the bureaucratic process for participating in the re-implementation of SOCIAL4FOOD training activities.
2	Bringing the youth to dialogue with the elders is an effective way of teaching them local cultural traditions.	The project provided a wonderful learning experience for the beneficiaries (mainly children) but also for the teachers (elders and local producers).	Low participation of teenagers in the SOCIAL4FOOD training activities and co-creation events. An effective engagement strategy specifically addressed to adolescents should be developed and implemented by using more digital technologies for attracting their interests.
3	Strengthening community legitimacy in decision-making	The co-creation events helped build understanding and consensus around the social farming design and management.	

5.1.2. Dissemination of lessons learnt (EITHE 15.1)

Dissemination of the results, lessons learnt, and good practice of the project has been performed through the project website, the social media accounts dedicated to the project (Facebook and Twitter), research article publications, and the final outreach event.

5.1.2.1. *Illustrate the implementation of the project with pictures/graphic/image/ infographics – A picture is worth a thousand words! It is highly recommended to make efficient use of pictures/graphic/image/ infographics in social medial or any other channel.*

Some photos of the Open Day event organized on July 29th, 2022

Presentation of the SOCIAL4FOOD activities - adults and adolescents' session

First step of the co-creation of the social farm (Collection of experiences and elicitation of ideas) - adults and adolescents' session

Sharing of ideas - adults and adolescents' session

Voting of ideas – adults and adolescents' session

Storytelling of experiences – children session

Collection of tips - children session

Drawings – children session

Some photos of the social laboratories organized on August 18th, 2022 and September 24th, 2022

Laboratory "I learn how to grow the fagiolina"

Land preparation

Sowing

Covering the seeds

Building of the “conocchie” (support scaffold for the growth of the plant)

Reflective Observation

Abstract Conceptualization

- ARATURA
 - FRESATURA
 - SOLCATURA (distanza 100 cm da un sodo e l'altro) usare TOPPA
 - X 50 semi dritti → PALI CON FILO
 - SEMINA → TUBO DI PASTICA dove si SEMINANO I FAGIOLI stando in piedi: se ne piantano 5 a distanza di 40-50 cm di distanza. Fagioli ricoperti con la terra.
 - SARCHIATURA = ZAPPA LA PIANTA e creare canale di irrigazione
 - "CONOCCHIATURA": si creano 4 canne come sostegno x la PIANTA che si arrampica con le corde.
 - INNAFFIATURA → IN BASE AL TERRENO
 - RACCOLTA = LA FAGIOLINA E' SECCA

DIFFICOLTA'

- UTILIZZO ZAPPA
 - FATICA FISICA

ASPETTI POSITIVI
 IMPARARE LA CULTURA ARABIANA E
 A USARE GLI ATTREZZI AGRICOLI

DIARIO di VIAGGIO di CAMILLA

ARATURA DEL TERRENO
 - FRESATURA DEL TERRENO
 - SOLCATURA (distanza 60 cm)
 SOLCO FATTO CON CANNUCCE, FILO E ZAPPA
 PER PIANTE I FAGIOLI ABBIAMO USATO UN TUBO PER NON CURVARCI. (SEMINA) IN OGNI BUCIA CIRCA 5 FAGIOLI.
 SOLCO PROFONDO 10 CM.
 I SEMI VENGONO RICOPERTI CON LA TERRA.
 SI ASPETTA CHE LA PIANTINA CRESCA UN PO' SENZA FARE LE CORDE (SARCHIATURA) = ZAPPARE LA PIANTINA. ~~VIENE~~ VIENE CREATO IL CANALE PER FAR SCORRERE L'ACQUA
 - CONOCCHIATURA = 4 PALI ATTACCATI TRA LORO PER FAR CRESCERE LE CORDE DELLA PIANTA

DIFFICOLTA' INFILARE LE CANNE NEL TERRENO

FATICA FISICA C'ERA TROPPO SOLE PERCIO' HO SOFFERTO TANTISSIMO

ASPETTI POSITIVI STARE NELLA NATURA ED AVERE IMPARATO UNA NUOVA CULTURA

DIARIO DI VIAGGIO
 DI :

ARATURA TERRENO
 - FRESATURA TERRENO
 → SOLCATURA dis. 60 CM
 - PER FARE IL SOLCO DRITTO ABBIAMO USATO LA ZAPPA
 + SEMINA: SI PRENDE UN TUBO CHE SERVE A SEMINARE I FAGIOLI SENZA FARE I FAGIOLI SE NE PIANTE 5 A DISTANZA DI 40 o 50 CM.
 • RICOPERTA DEI SEMI CON LA TERRA SCANATA
 - "SARCHIATURA" = ZAPPARE LA PIANTINA E CREARE IL CANALE PER L'IRRIGAZIONE
 - "CONOCCHIATURA": LE "CONOCCHIE" SONO DEL CANNE CHE SERVONO PER FAR CRESCERE E FAR ARRAMPICARE LA FAGIOLINA
DIFFICOLTA': METTERE LE CANNE

Laboratory "I learn how to cook the fagiolina"

Preparation of the sauce

Preparation of the hand-made pasta

Final baking

Reflective Observation

Abstract Conceptualization

Laboratory "I learn how to harvest the fagiolina"

Concrete Experience

Reflective Observation

Abstract Conceptualization

Some photos of the SOCIAL4FOOD competition organized on September 4th, 2022

Some photos of the second step of the co-design of the social farm organized on September 24th, 2022.

Presentation of the results of first step of the co-creation activities

Collection of possible solutions

Collaborative discussion and definition of a shared solution

“Fagiolina Ambassadors” appointment

Some photos of the third step of the co-design of the social farm organized on October 29th, 2022.

Some photos of the final outreach event organized on November 26th, 2022.

Presentation of the obtained results from the SOCIAL4FOOD project

Round table with the Mayor of Arsoli and the Mayors of the neighboring towns

*5.1.3. Dissemination and communication activities and number of people in these activities
(EITHE 17.1)*

The dissemination and communication activities of the project that are implemented are the project website, the social media accounts (Facebook and Twitter), the final outreach event, the communication material (brochure and short videos), and scientific publications.

The number of people reached through the project website and the social media accounts is: 48 people from the project website, 174 people joined the SOCIAL4FOOD Facebook group, and 30 followers of the Twitter account.

The final outreach event, organized in a hybrid way (both online and in presence) on November 26th 2022, has been attended by 61 people (45 participants online and 16 participants in presence). During the event, the obtained results from the SOCIAL4FOOD project have been shown to participants. A round table with the Mayor of Arsoli and the Mayors of the neighboring towns (Agosta, Anticoli Corrado, Camerata Nuova, Riofreddo, and Rocca Canterano) has been carried out to transfer the co-creation methodology used in the project for stimulating the transfer of transgenerational knowledge and the production of the typical local food of the other territories.

The communication material (brochures and short promotional videos) has been provided. The brochures (150 copies) have been printed and distributed to the Arsoli community. Three short promotional videos have been created and posted on Youtube (<https://www.youtube.com/@social4foodproject>) and the project website. The videos received 243 visualizations and 129 likes on Youtube.

Two scientific articles showcasing project outputs are in the process of being drafted and will be submitted to two topic-specific open-access journals (Sustainability <https://www.mdpi.com/journal/sustainability> and Societies <https://www.mdpi.com/journal/societies>) by the end of December 2022.

5.1.3.1. Attendance sheets; the list of participants of each Citizen Engagement activities, events, workshops, etc.,

Attendance sheets (adults and children) of the Open Day event organized on July 29th, 2022

Nome	Cognome	ETA	Firma
MARIA	LOTTI	71	Maria L. Lotti
ROBERTO	PUCCINI	68	Rob. Puccini
ANTONIO	CHITI	84	Antonio Chiti
ALBERTO	TARQUINI	83	Alberto Tarquini
PIETRO	CERRONI	54	Pietro Cerroni
VALENTINA	ZUCCHINI	34	Valentina Zucchini
TOMMASO	CERRONI	15	Tommaso Cerroni
MARCO	DI NARDO	15	Marco Di Nardo
ANGELO	BERNARDINI	21	Angelo Bernardini
DORIA	BILLO	66	Doria Billo
MARZIA	ZITTO	64	Marzia Zitto
PIERLUIGI	DOLZIA	28	Pierluigi Dolzia
ALESSANDRO	AMICI	21	Alessandro Amici
NAPOLIONE	MARINO	75	Napoli Marini
GIORGIO	CAVALLI	48	Giorgio Cavalli
PAOLO	NAPOLITANO	56	Paolo Napolitano
SYRIA	ALIMONTI	19	Syria Alimonti
MARCO	PROIETTI	48	Marco Proietti
DORINDA	D'UZZO	17	Dorinda D'Uzzo
CLAUDIA	GREGORI	29	Claudia Gregori
BEATRICE MARIA	DE SANTIS	20	Beatrice Maria De Santis
CHIARA	BONNI	42	Chiara Bonni

NOME	COGNOME	ETA
GINEVRA	MASTRECCHIA	9
ROBERTO	MASI	8
JAMUELE	DE SOUTI	10
DAVIDE	BAIACCO	12
ROCCO	ALFOUSO	10
VALENTINA	NAPOLEONI	8
CRISTIAN	PROIETTI	12
CECILIA	//	8
CARILIA	MASI	10
MARCO	PROIETTI	11
CARILIA	CAUCCI	12
LUDOVICO	CAUCCI	9
UTTOLOA	BERGAMASCHI	11
CARLOTTA	//	8
DAMIANO	MAGGIAM	8
GINEVRA	LAURETTI	10

Attendance sheets (adults and children) of social laboratories organized on August 18th, 2022

Participants in the laboratory: the cultivation techniques of the "fagiolina arsolana"

FOGLIO PRESENZA ADULTI EVENTO 18 AGOSTO 2022				
NOME	COGNOME	ETA'	FIRMA	E-MAIL
VALENTINA	CALABARA	36	Valentina Calabara	valentina.calabara@gmail.com
EUGENIA	ALIMONTI	55	Eugenia Alimonti	eugenialimonti@gmail.com
BENEDETTA	TUZZA	71	Benedetta Tuzza	
RITA	DI MARCO	67	Rita Di Marco	
DORIA	BILLO	66	Doria Billo	
CAROLINA	FRANCINI	73	Carolina Francini	
MARIA LUIGIA	DI SICCARI	71	Maria Luigia Di Sicari	
MARIA ANTONIETTA	MASI	75	Maria Antonietta Masi	
DECCA	DECCA	53	Decca Decca	
TAMARA	PASSERI	45	Tamara Passeri	
AUSONIO	NOZZI	64	Ausonio Nozzi	
FRANCO	MANZI	20	Franco Manzi	FRANCO.MANZI@GMAIL.COM
NICOLETTA	MINATI	32	Nicoletta Minati	NIC.MINATI@GMAIL.COM
VALENTINA	PASCALI	34	Valentina Pascali	valentina.pascali@gmail.com
ROLANDO	PASSERI	51	Rolando Passeri	
CARILIA	TOMASINI	46	Carilia Tomasini	CARILIA.TOMASINI@FIRMA.IT
SERENA	PROIETTI	39	Serena Proietti	
ALBERTO	TARQUINI	83	Alberto Tarquini	
GIOVANNA	TARQUINI	42	Giovanna Tarquini	
LAURA	ZUCCHINI	35	Laura Zucchini	
JUAN CARLOS	BURNIA MOLINA	47	Juan Carlos Burnia Molina	
PIACENTINI	BERNARDINI	72	Piacentini Bernardini	

OTTAVIA	ORTISI	36	Ottavia Ortisi	
ANNA MARIA	ZECCHI	51	Anna Maria Zecchi	
GIULIA	D'ANTONI	28	Giulia D'Antoni	
FEDERICA	COLAPANESSE	29	Federica Colapanesse	
DAMA	BONNI	53	Dama Bonni	
PAOLA	FERRI	69	Paola Ferri	
EUSA	DI GIUSEPPE	38	Eusa Di Giuseppe	
NATHASCHA	NARDONI	41	Nathascha Nardoni	
MARIO	NAPOLEONI	75	Mario Napoleoni	
MIRKO	LUPI	42	Mirko Lupi	
FABIO	DE SANTIS	40	Fabio De Santis	
MARIA ANTONIETTA	MASI	76	Maria Antonietta Masi	
ERICA	PROIETTI	63	Erica Proietti	
DANIELA	MASINI	43	Daniela Masini	
GIULIA	GIANNI	60	Giulia Gianni	
VALENTINA	NAPOLEONI	39	Valentina Napoleoni	
MAURIZIO	NOZZI	50	Maurizio Nozzi	
LOREDANA	BURNIA	63	Loredana Burnia	
ANNA MARIA	RINELLI	65	Anna Maria Rinelli	
CHIARA	BONNI	42	Chiara Bonni	

FOGLIO PRESENZA MINORI EVENTO 18 AGOSTO 2022

NOME	COGNOME	ETA'
ROBERTO	MASI	8
DAMIANO	HAGGAM	8
COSTANZA	BORGHI	7
ADELE	DESANTIS	3
LUCA	LUCCI	7
MARCO	//	5
FRANCESCO	PETRI	4
PABLO	D'ASCENZI	3,5
AURORA	BUCCHIA LUCCIANO	5
ECLA	//	6
CAMILLA	MASI	10
LORENZO	PASSARELLI	10
MATEO	LUPI	8
ANGELICA	CECCOM	6
MANUEL	DE ANGENS	6
NARLOONI	CARLOTTI	6
MARY	CATULLA	10
LUIGI	CAUCCI	8
GEMMA	MASTRECCIA	9
OMERO	AMICI	8
MELISSA	PIACENTINI	6
PARIDE	FRIGUCCI	4

Participants in the laboratory: the cooking of local recipes of the "fagiolina arsolana"

FOGLIO PRESENZA ADULTI EVENTO 18 AGOSTO 2022

NOME	COGNOME	ETA'	FIRMA	E-MAIL
DAMIANO	MASI	51	<i>[Signature]</i>	damiano.masi@gmail.com
CHIARA	BONNI	42	<i>[Signature]</i>	chiara.bonni@gmail.com
RODOLFO	PASSERI	51	<i>[Signature]</i>	
ROMINA	D'ARBELO	44	<i>[Signature]</i>	romina.d'arbelo@gmail.com
EUGENIA	CHITTI	63	<i>[Signature]</i>	eugenia.chitti@gmail.com
NICOLETTA	SIMBOLI	40	<i>[Signature]</i>	nicoletta.simboli@gmail.com
FRANCESCA	CENSI	40	<i>[Signature]</i>	francesca.censi@gmail.com
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FABIO	DESANTIS	40	<i>[Signature]</i>	fabio.desantis@gmail.com
NICOLETTA	HINATI	32	<i>[Signature]</i>	nicolettahinati@gmail.com
PIETRO	CERRONI	54	<i>[Signature]</i>	pietro.cerroni@gmail.com
AUGUSTO	MASI	62	<i>[Signature]</i>	augusto.masi@gmail.com
SAURO	SPARDELLA	76	<i>[Signature]</i>	sauro.spardezza@gmail.com
FRANCESCO	GAN		<i>[Signature]</i>	francesco.gan@gmail.com
ANNA	ZUCCHETTI	44	<i>[Signature]</i>	anna.zucchetti@gmail.com
DAFNE	TARQUINI	51	<i>[Signature]</i>	dafne.tarquini@gmail.com
VITTORIO	PROIETTI	55	<i>[Signature]</i>	vittorio.proietti@gmail.com
MARCO	PROIETTI	48	<i>[Signature]</i>	marco.proietti@gmail.com

FOGLIO PRESENZA MINORI EVENTO 18 AGOSTO 2022

NOME	COGNOME	ETA'
LUIGI	CAUCCI	9
CAMILLA	//	12
DARIO	AMICI	8
GEMMA	MASTRECCIA	9
ANDREA	PROIETTI	11
ADELE	DESANTIS	3
ROBERTO	MASI	8
TOMMASO	CERBONI	15

Attendance sheets (adults and children) of the SOCIAL4FOOD competition organized on September 4th, 2022

FOGLIO PRESENZA ADULTI EVENTO 04 SETTEMBRE 2022

NOME	COGNOME	ETA'	FIRMA	E-MAIL
NICOLETTA	MINATI	32	<i>Nicola Minati</i>	nic.minati@gmail.com
FABIO	DESANTIS	40	<i>Fabio Desantis</i>	DESANTISF35@gmail.com
CRISTINA	DI PROVO	30	<i>Crystina</i>	crystina.di.provo@gmail.com
CLAUDIA	GREGORI	29	<i>Claudia</i>	claudia.gregori@gmail.com
FEDERICA	CAMPARANESCHI	28	<i>Federica</i>	federica.camparaneschi@gmail.com
GABRIELE	CECCONI	28	<i>Gabriele</i>	gabriele.ceconi@gmail.com
FEDERICA	BONM	45	<i>Federica</i>	fedra.bonm@univ.it
MARCO	PROIETTI	48	<i>Marco</i>	proetti.marco@gmail.com
ARIANNA	CENUSI	46	<i>Arianna</i>	arianna.cenusi@gmail.com
FABRIZIO	CAUCCI	48	<i>Fabrizio</i>	caucci.fabrizio@gmail.com
ETILIA	COSTANTINI	40	<i>Etilia</i>	emilio.costantini@gmail.com
TAMARA	PASSERI	45	<i>Tamara</i>	
MARIO	D'UBARO	50	<i>Mario</i>	
VALENTINA	CINELLI	43	<i>Valentina</i>	

FOGLIO PRESENZA MINORI EVENTO 04 SETTEMBRE 2022

NOME	COGNOME	ETA'
ADELE	DESANTIS	3
GINEVRA	MASTRECCHIA	9
ALEXANDRA	CECONI	5
ROCCO	ALFONSI	11
ANDREA	PROIETTI	11
CLOE	BRUM	11
CAMILLA	MASI	10
SAMUELE	DESOUKI	11
LORENZO	INSPRECH	10
LEONARDO	PASSARELLI	12
GIULIA	TOSI	11
GIULIA	IASI	3
LUDOVICO	CAUCCI	9
DAMIANO	MAGGIARI	8

	ANDREA	D'UBARO	9
	ISABELLA	DI CENUSI	11
	GIOGIATA	DE SOUKI	9
	UOLA	IACOBACCI	9
	MAYA	TARQUINI	12
	ANNA	IACOBACCI	6

Attendance sheets (adults and children) of the laboratory: the harvesting techniques of the "fagiolina arsolana" organized on September 24th, 2022.

FOGLIO PRESENZA ADULTI EVENTO 24 SETTEMBRE 2022

Laboratorio

NOME	COGNOME	ETA'	FIRMA	E-MAIL
SAURO	SBARDELLA	24	<i>Sauro</i>	SBASAURO@gmail.com
MARIA	NAPOLITANI	75	<i>Maria</i>	maria.napolitano@gmail.com
PETRO	CERRONI	54	<i>Pietro</i>	petro.cerroni@gmail.com
VALENTINA	POUCANI	34	<i>Valentina</i>	valentina.poucani@gmail.com
ANUNZIATA	ERCO	64	<i>Anunziata</i>	erco.annunziata@gmail.com
AUGUSTO	MASI	60	<i>Augusto</i>	masi.augusto@gmail.com
MAURIZIO	AMICI	50	<i>Maurizio</i>	
MARCO	PROIETTI	48	<i>Marco</i>	proetti.marco@gmail.com

FOGLIO PRESENZA MINORI EVENTO 24 SETTEMBRE 2022

Laboratorio

NOME	COGNOME	ETA'
ROCCO	ALFONSI	11
TOMMASO	CERRONI	15
GINEVRA	MASTRECCHIA	9
DARIO	AMICI	8
ANDREA	PROIETTI	11
MARCO	D'UBARO	15

Attendance sheets (adults and children) of the second step of the co-design of the social farm organized on September 24th, 2022.

FOGLIO PRESENZA ADULTI EVENTO 24 SETTEMBRE 2022
Co-creazione dell'orto sociale

NOME	COGNOME	ETA'	FIRMA	E-MAIL
Valeria	Pollicani	60	[Signature]	
Valeria	Pollicani	34	[Signature]	
Mario	Napoleoni	75	[Signature]	
Spino	Sbarone	24	[Signature]	
Aurelio	Masi	61	[Signature]	
Fabrizio	Proietti	74	[Signature]	
Pietro	Cerroni	54		
Rolando	Passeri	51	[Signature]	
Angela	Bernardini	81	[Signature]	
Alexia	Mitoleoni	39	[Signature]	
Bonica	Bram	45	[Signature]	
Cecilia	Amici	79	[Signature]	

FOGLIO PRESENZA MINORI EVENTO 24 SETTEMBRE 2022
Co-creazione dell'orto sociale

NOME	COGNOME	ETA'
CAMILIA	MASI	10
GINEVA	MASRECCIA	9
ANDREA	PROIETTI	11
DARIO	AMICI	8
NOCCO	ALFONSI	11
TOMMASO	CERRONI	15
MARCO	DI MARDO	15
GNETA	TOSI	11
LORENZO	PASAPPELLI	10
DANILO	MARANI	8

Attendance sheets (adults and children) of the third step of the co-design of the social farm organized on October 29th, 2022.

FOGLIO FIRMA EVENTO 29 OTTOBRE 2022 – ADULTI

NOME	COGNOME	ETA'	E-MAIL
Fabrizio	Proietti	74	f.proietti@epuail.com
Paola	Pollicani	59	paola.pollicani@gmail.com
Elisabetta	Allorani	55	elisabetta.allorani@gmail.com
Hicenia	D'Antoni	32	hicenia.dantoni@epuail.com
Valentina	Pollicani	36	valentina.pollicani@gmail.com
Mario	Napoleoni	75	mario.napoleoni@gmail.com

FOGLIO FIRMA EVENTO 29 OTTOBRE 2022 – BAMBINI

NOME	COGNOME	ETA'
GINEVIA	MASRECCIA	9
CAMILIA	MASI	

Attendance sheets (adults and children in presence) of the final outreach event organized on November 26th, 2022.

Annex B: Questionnaire for adults and adolescents

The questionnaire for adults and adolescents consists of 19 items grouped under four different sections, plus a preliminary and an introductory section. Adults and adolescents

participating in the SOCIAL4FOOD activities were invited to respond to the questionnaire either using a paper form or an online form

(https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfyVeYEZdb_ezV_FLh_E-rM7quVa4YfiWLDdjOBiftTO-VFXQ/viewform?usp=sf_link). The paper form of the questionnaire for adults and adolescents is provided below.

Questionario di gradimento delle attività del progetto SOCIAL4FOOD – adulti e adolescenti

Con il seguente questionario, rigorosamente anonimo, vogliamo rilevare il grado di soddisfazione dei partecipanti alle attività del progetto SOCIAL4FOOD. Ti invitiamo a rispondere alle domande, segnando la risposta per te più rispondente o almeno più vicina alle tue opinioni.

GENERE

- maschio femmina altro

FASCIA D'ETA

- 14-18
- 19-59
- da 60 in su

PARTE INTRODUTTIVA

- Rispetto alle aspettative che avevi prima di partecipare alle attività del progetto SOCIAL4FOOD, queste sono state confermate?

- moltissimo molto abbastanza poco

per niente

- I contenuti appresi durante le attività del progetto:

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco
per niente

Se hai risposto poco o per niente, pensi che la durata degli eventi doveva essere

maggiore minore

Commento _____

- Giudichi adeguati gli ambienti offerti per lo svolgimento degli eventi organizzati (laboratori, sfida culinaria ed eventi di co-creazione)?

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco
per niente

Commento _____

PARTE II: AUTOVALUTAZIONE

- Partecipando ai laboratori e alla sfida culinaria hai acquisito

nuove conoscenze:

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco
per niente

nuove abilità:

- moltissimo molto abbastanza poco
per niente

- Che tipo di conoscenze hai acquisito?
-

- Che tipo di abilità hai acquisito?
-

- Partecipando agli eventi di co-creazione, li hai ritenuti utili per condividere le tue idee?

- moltissimo molto abbastanza poco
per niente

Se hai risposto poco o per niente, cosa suggerisci per migliorare?

- Partecipando agli eventi di co-creazione, pensi di avere contribuito attivamente alla co-creazione dell'orto sociale?

- moltissimo molto abbastanza
 poco per niente

Se hai risposto poco o per niente, cosa suggerisci per migliorare?

- Quanto ti soddisfa la soluzione proposta per gestire ed organizzare l'orto sociale?

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco

per niente

Se hai risposto poco o per niente, che cosa non ti soddisfa?

PARTE III: VALUTAZIONE DEGLI EVENTI ORGANIZZATI

- Gli eventi organizzati (laboratori, sfida culinaria ed eventi di co-creazione) sono stati interessanti?

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco

per niente

Se hai risposto poco o per niente, cosa suggerisci per migliorare?

- Le conoscenze che hai acquisito durante gli eventi organizzati (laboratori, sfida culinaria ed eventi di co-creazione) sono state utili?

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco
per niente

- Sei riuscito a mettere in pratica le conoscenze che hai acquisito durante gli eventi organizzati (laboratori, sfida culinaria ed eventi di co-creazione)?

Sì No

Se hai risposto sì, come?

- Hai incontrato difficoltà nello svolgere le attività proposte negli eventi organizzati (laboratori, sfida culinaria ed eventi di co-creazione)?

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco
per niente

Se hai risposto moltissimo, molto o abbastanza, quali difficoltà hai incontrato?

- Durante gli eventi organizzati (laboratori, sfida culinaria ed eventi di co-creazione) si è creato un clima di partecipazione positivo?

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco
per niente

Se hai risposto poco o per niente, cosa suggerisci per migliorare?

PARTE IV: SODDISFAZIONE GENERALE

- Quanto sei soddisfatto delle attività svolte negli eventi organizzati (laboratori, sfida culinaria ed eventi di co-creazione)?

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco
per niente

- Quanto pensi sia opportuno riproporre le attività negli anni successivi?

moltissimo molto abbastanza poco
per niente

Annex C: Questionnaire for children

The questionnaire for children consists of 12 items grouped under four different sections, plus an introductory section, as shown below.

Questionario di gradimento delle attività del progetto SOCIAL4FOOD - bambini

Ti chiediamo di rispondere alle domande che trovi di seguito.

PARTE INTRODUTTIVA

- Ti è piaciuta questa esperienza sulla fagiolina arsolana?

- Ti piacerebbe rifare nei prossimi anni esperienze simili?

PARTE I: VALUTAZIONE DEGLI EVENTI ORGANIZZATI

Durante il progetto sono stati organizzati 3 laboratori (sulla coltivazione, sulla cucina e sulla raccolta della fagiolina) e una sfida di cucina.

- Ti sei divertito durante i laboratori?

- Quale è la cosa che ti ha divertito di più?

- E quella che ti ha divertito di meno?

- Ti sei divertito durante la sfida di cucina?

- Quale è la cosa che ti ha divertito di più?
-

- E quella che ti ha divertito di meno?
-

PARTE II: ORGANIZZAZIONE

- Avresti voluto partecipare ad un numero maggiore di laboratori?

- Avresti voluto partecipare ad un numero maggiore di sfide?

- Il tempo che hai avuto a disposizione per svolgere le attività è stato sufficiente?

PARTE III: AUTOVALUTAZIONE

- Hai incontrato delle difficoltà durante i laboratori?

- Quali difficoltà hai incontrato?
-

- Pensi di aver imparato qualcosa di nuovo sulla fagiolina arsolana?

- Che cosa hai imparato?
-

PARTE IV: SODDISFAZIONE GENERALE

- Ti piacerebbe avere a disposizione un orto dove svolgere attività insieme ai tuoi compagni, alla scuola, agli anziani e agli agricoltori?

- Ti sei trovato/a bene con gli altri bambini e bambine?

- Ti è piaciuto stare insieme agli anziani ed imparare da loro?

Annex D: Interview

The interview schedule consisted of 5 questions investigating the advantages, difficulties, and replicability of the project's results. In the following table the questions are provided:

Question A	What is your overall opinion on the Social4Food project?
Question B	What are the benefits of the project to the community of Arsoli?
Question C	Have you encountered any negative aspects or difficulties in carrying out the project activities? If so, what could be improved?
Question D	Do you think it is appropriate to repeat the project activities in the following years?
Question E	Do you think the results obtained from the project can be applied to neighboring local communities?

Annex E: Screenshot of the visitors of the project website

Annex F: Brochure

SOCIAL4FOOD

Co-progettazione di un orto sociale per riqualificare uno spazio verde abbandonato e migliorare l'estetica del territorio e la qualità della vita della comunità locale

Contattaci

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Dott.ssa Arianna D'Ulizia
arianna.dulizia@irpps.cnr.it

Seguici

Sito web:
<https://cnrirpps.wixsite.com/social4food>
Twitter: Social4FoodP
Facebook: SOCIAL4FOOD project group

PROGETTO SOCIAL4FOOD

Agricoltura sociale per stimolare il trasferimento transgenerazionale delle conoscenze e la produzione di prodotti tipici locali

Migliorare la conoscenza delle tradizioni locali con la partecipazione sociale e il dialogo transgenerazionale

Chi siamo

SOCIAL4FOOD è un progetto finanziato nell'ambito del bando New European Bauhaus - Citizen Engagement e sviluppato con il sostegno di EIT Food. Il progetto, ideato e realizzato dal gruppo di Informatica Sociale dell'Istituto di Ricerche sulla Popolazione e le Politiche Sociali (Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche), è supportato dal Comune di Arsoli, dalla Pro Loco di Arsoli, dal Centro anziani di Arsoli e dall'Associazione "Amici della Fagiolina di Arsoli".

Scopo del progetto

Il progetto applica i principi del New European Bauhaus (sostenibilità, estetica, inclusione) per migliorare il contatto tra le giovani generazioni e gli spazi pubblici verdi, guidati dalla saggezza degli anziani. Attraverso una serie di attività di agricoltura sociale, il progetto mira a stimolare il coinvolgimento degli adolescenti arsolani (compresi anche i giovani immigrati) nella coltivazione e nella cucina collaborativa della "fagiolina arsolana".

Obiettivi del progetto

- i) Coinvolgimento dei cittadini nelle attività di formazione e co-creazione
- ii) Riqualificazione di spazi verdi abbandonati
- iii) Sperimentazione di una strategia di coinvolgimento dei cittadini per promuovere la cultura e la conoscenza dei cibi tipici locali e replicarla in altri contesti simili

Risultati ottenuti

- Definizione e applicazione di una metodologia di co-creazione;
- Partecipazione della cittadinanza arsolana (adolescenti, bambini e cittadini interessati) ai laboratori sociali verdi, alla sfida culinaria e alle attività di co-creazione dell'orto sociale;
- Realizzazione di un orto sociale inclusivo e sostenibile

Valorizzazione dei risultati

- Incontri periodici con gli amministratori locali dei comuni limitrofi per il trasferimento dei risultati;
- Incontri periodici con i rappresentanti delle Istituzioni/Associazioni locali per il mantenimento dell'orto sociale ed il proseguimento delle attività del progetto.

5.3. Contribution to the mandatory Core EIT KPIs

KPI Code and name	KPI description	KPI Target value	Planned project contribution according to the Application Form	Real project contribution at the end of month 3 (September 2022)
EITHE 14.1 Good practices and lessons learnt identified and codified by the project.	Number of good practices ³ and lessons learnt ⁴ identified and codified by the project. Structured data: ✓ List incl. the type, title and short description	1	The project provides 1 best practice that is the co-creation methodology (Activity 3) and 1 Lessons learnt from the implementation and follow-up of the co-creation methodology during the SLOWFOOD training activities and the social farm	1 best practice defined, which is the co-creation methodology (Activity 3), and 3 Lessons learnt from the implementation and follow-up of the co-creation methodology during the SLOWFOOD training activities and the social farm.
EITHE 15.1 Results, lessons learnt, and good practices disseminated by the project through appropriate means (e.g., publications, online repositories, fact sheets, targeted	Number of results, good practices and lessons learnt disseminated Structured data: ✓ List incl. the type, title, List of the website links showing the dissemination	1	Results, good practices and lessons learnt disseminated through the following 4 means of communication: - the project website; - social media accounts dedicated to the project; - research article publication - final outreach event	Results disseminated through the following 3 means of communication: - the project website; - social media accounts dedicated to the project; - final outreach event. 2 research article publications (in progress)

³ Good practice is a practice that has been proven to work well and produce good results and is therefore recommended as a model.

⁴ Lessons learnt are an analysis / record of a learning process in the development, implementation and follow-up of an innovative approach, process or activity. Lessons learnt are often a by-product of identifying and validating good practices

workshops etc.)				
EITHE 17.1 Number of dissemination and communication activities of the project and number of people reached through these activities	Structured data:			
	✓ Physical or online event title and number of its participants	60	1 Physical Final outreach event (> 60 participants)	1 Physical/online final outreach event on November 26 th , 2022, attended by 61 people (45 participants online and 16 participants in presence)
	✓ Website/social media	1	1 Project website 1 Facebook account 1 Twitter account	1 Project website available at https://cnrirpps.wixsite.com/social4food/en ; 1 Facebook account available at https://www.facebook.com/groups/734039724347222 ; 1 Twitter account available at https://twitter.com/Social4foodP
	✓ Disseminated/communication material	1	1 Research article 1 brochure 1 short video	1 brochure (150 copies) printed and distributed to the Arsoli community. 3 short promotional videos created and posted on Youtube (https://www.youtube.com/@social4foodproject) and the project website. 2 scientific articles showcasing project outputs are in the process of being drafted and will be submitted to two topic-specific open-access journals (Sustainability

				<p>https://www.mdpi.com/journal/sustainability and Societies https://www.mdpi.com/journal/societies) by the end of December 2022.</p>
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